

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

REVIEW ON AYURVEDIC PRODUCT: SPECIAL FOCUS ON SKIN CARE PRODUCT.

Ms. Bhere Priyanka ., Ms. Bhongale Monali ., Dr. Ige Pradyumna

Abasaheb Kakade College of B. Pharmacy, Bodhegaon. Tal – Shevgaon, Dist – Ahmednagar , PIN- 414503.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 22/02/2023

Available online

02/03/2023

Keywords

Ayurveda,
Herbs,
Skin Care,
Medicinal Plant,
Dermatology.

ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is based on 3 principles PanchamahabhutaSidhhanta, Tridosha, Guna Rasa ViryaVipakaPrabhavaSidhhanta. Charak and Sushruta made significant contribution to Ayurveda. By Balancing tridoshas Ayurveda maintain the health of skin. The human skin plays significant role in physiological functions of sensation, protection and thermoregulation. The procedures of skin care given in the Ayurvedic classics are purely natural and they improve the skin health as compared to modern cosmetic products. Ayurvedic skin care products having a various therapeutic properties and are used for treatments of condition such as photosensitivity, ageing, finelines, wrinkles, dark spots, etc. A Large number of Ayurvedic product have been developed for skin care e.g. Asava – Arista, Avaleha. Paste, Natural Powder, Lepa. Some medicinal plants used in skin care are aloe vera, turmeric, ginger, neem, etc. They can be sold as tablet, powder, gels, sunscreen, creams, teas, etc. They are safe and effective. Many chemicals and synthetic ingredients used in many skin care product can cause variety of undesirable side effects. This review present the concept of Ayurvedic product which are natural and chemical free have number of benefits and healing repairing effects on skin. Ethnobotanical dermatology in India confirms the belief that their analysis will accelerate the discovery of new effective therapeutic agents for skin care.

Corresponding author

Bhere Priyanka

Abasaheb Kakade College of B. Pharmacy,
Bodhegaon. Tal – Shevgaon, Dist – Ahmednagar, PIN- 414503.
bherepp2019@gmail.com
7820841141

Please cite this article in press as **Bhere Priyanka et al.** Review on Ayurvedic Product: Special Focus on Skin Care Product. . Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. 2023;13(02).

Copy right © 2023 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

The word 'Veda' means Knowledge. The evolution of the Indian art of healing and living a healthy life comes from the four Vedas namely; Rigveda, Samaveda, Yajurveda, Atharvaveda. Ayurveda is attributed to Dhanvantari the physician to the god's in Hindu mythology, who received it from Bramha. Its earliest concepts were set out in the portion of the veda's known as the Atharvaveda. The name Ayurveda is derived from the sanskrit word 'Ayur' means 'Life' and 'Veda' means 'knowledge' or 'Science'. It is the Science of Life that teaches us to live in a truly balanced, natural and harmonious state. There are eight branches of Ayurveda (Flowchart 1).

Flowchart 1: Eight Branches of Ayurveda.

Ayurveda is based on the three principles : A) Panchmahabhuta Siddhanta B) Tridosha Theory C) Guna Rasa Virya Vipaka Prabhava Siddhanta

Panchmahabhuta Siddhanta :

Ayurveda follows the five great elements known as **Panchamahabhutas**. They are present in human body. They are Akash (Space), Vayu (Air), Jal (Water), Agni (Fire), Prithvi (Earth). Combination of these five great elements form seven basic tissues of the body which are referred as 'SaptaDahu' (Flow Chart 2).

Flow Chart 2: Sapta Dahu In Ayurveda.

Tridosha Theory :

According to this theory the five great elements (Panchamahabhuta) exist in human body in three different forms. They are together known as Tridosha (Figure 1). They are -Vata (Space + air), Pitta (Fire + Liquid), Kapha (Liquid + Solid). These tridosha when present in balanced form in the body is considered as healthy condition, any imbalance in tridosha is considered as disease condition. Ayurveda tries to maintain the balance in these elements.

Vata : It regulates the psychic and nervous system. Imbalance of this leads to disease of ENT, heart, urinary tract, skin, etc

Pitta : It regulates energy production, digestion, tissue building, etc. Imbalance of this leads to disease of like acidity, indigestion, liver and skin disease.

Kapha : It regulates heat formation of fluids, mucous, etc. Imbalance of this results in joint pain, brain disease, drowsiness, etc.

Ayurvedic Clock

Figure 1) Ayurvedic Clock.

Guna Rasa Virya Vipaka Prabhava Sidhanta :

These are considered as five pharmacological principles / properties of ‘Dravya’ (Drug Substance). They are Rasa (Taste), Guna (Taste), Virya (Active Principle), Vipaka (Digestive Products), Prabhava (Pharmaco Therapeutic Action). Charak and Sushruta made significant contributions to Ayurveda. The book ‘Charak Samhita’ was written by Charaka and he was known as Father Of Ayurveda.

Sushruta Samhita :

Sushruta (the physician) is famous for knowledge of plastic surgery, owing to his writing and experimenting with a particular science. The sushrutasamhita is the most representative work of the hindu system of medicine, it is recognized as the first authoritative book on Ayurveda.

Charak Samhita :

Charaka is the renowned author of the oldest surviving text in Ayurveda, the charakasamhita. Charak Samhita is a comprehensive guide that contains details of an overall ideology, approach treatment methods and general advice for physician. It is believed that his master, Punarvaju, Atreya had seven disciples (Flowchart 3).

Flowchart 3: Seven disciples according to Punarvaju, Atreya.

Sushruta Samhita :

Sushruta (the physician) is famous for knowledge of plastic surgery, owing to his writing and experimenting with a particular science. The sushrutasamhita is the most representative work of the hindu system of medicine, it is recognized as the first authoritative book on Ayurveda.

Ayurvedic Regimes For Skin Care :

Skin is the first thing which comes in view when meeting or just visualizing someone. Ayurvedic herbs and their significance is popular world wide. The procedures of skin care given in the Ayurvedic classics are purely natural and they improve the skin health as compared to modern cosmetic products. Ayurvedic skin care products treatments for condition such as photosensitivity, ageing, finelines, wrinkles, hyper-pigmentation, dark spots, etc. In Ayurveda, 'Twacha' word is used for skin. Twacha is derived from 'Tvac' dhatu, which means 'cover'. Skin contains sweat glands, blood vessel, hair follicles which are responsible for functioning of skin. (2) Any abnormality in them leads to skin disease. Skin care regimes comprises of following concepts which available in Ayurveda as:

A) Dincharya: It includes following procedure for routine skin care

a) Mukhprakashalana (Face Wash)- Washing the face with cold water and some specific drugs of Amalki etc. prevent acne, dryness, pigmentation.

b) Nasya -Nasya which is indicated in Dincharya is PratimarshaNasya. Oil is used for Nasya is anu tail.

c) Gandusha - Oil is used for Gandushais tiltaila which checks dryness of throat, cracking of lip's.

d) Abhyanga – It provide softness to the body, cleanliness, strength and improves the complexion.

e) Vyayama (Exercise) – vyayama is considered for building up health of the body and gives strength as well.

f) Aalepana – It provides cheerfulness, eventone , complexion, strength, and eliminate dead cells and fatigue.

g) Snana – Bathing with cold water with Amalaki will surely get rid of wrinkled skin.

B) Ritucharya : Different ritus has been elaborated in details in Ayurveda. Sixritus which are described in Ayurveda. Following are the different regimes as per Ritu (Flowchart 4). HemantaRitu (Paste of seeds of badar, vasaka root), ShishirRitu (Kateri root, Black Til), VasantRitu (Paste of dabh, Saunf, Chaval), GrishmaRitu (Kumud, Durva, Chandana), VarshaRitu (Jatamanasi, Tagar, Padmak), SharadRitu (Mulethi, Tagar, Khas). [1]

Flowchart 4 :Different Regimes As Per Ritu.

Ethnodermatological Use of Medicinal Plants:

Ethnodermatological used of medicinal plants in India is still a subject to conduct more studies to see if there is chemical, microbiological or clinical evidence from a scientific perspective of their effectiveness for those skin disorder.

Approximately 25% of contemporary pharmaceuticals are derived directly or indirectly from plants. It has been reported by the Botanical Survey Of India (BSI) that out of the 45,000 plant species listed, at least 30,000 are of high interest because of therapeutic potential. Ethnodermatology is a section of ethno medicine and ethnobiology related to the diagnosis and treatment of various skin diseases /infections skin care.

Most important part of ethnodermatology is traditional knowledge of medicinal plant and their applications for several skin diseases in India. Depending on dermatology ethnomedical used of plants have been confirmed by several pharmacological, clinical and preclinical studies (Figure 2). [3]

Figure 2) Ethnodermatological Drugs By Plant Families Used In India.

Herbal Drugs For Skin Care Product:

Herb is a plant or any part of the plant for its fragrance, flavor or therapeutic properties. They are sold as tablet, cases, powders, teas. Ayurveda utilizes numerous species to make beautifying agents for beautification and security from outside impacts (Table 1).

Table 1. Herbs For Derma Care.

Sr.No.	Properties	Herbs
1)	Anti- Ageing	Guduchi, Ashwagandha, Amla, Turmeric, Ginseng
2)	Anti-Acne	Neem, Aloe Vera, Lemon Grass, Amaranth
3)	Antiseptic	Clove, Cinnamon, Turmeric, Fennel, Ginger, Eucalyptus ,
4)	Antioxidant	Cloves, Cinnamon, Turmeric, Rosemary, Vanilla Bean
5)	Anti- Inflammatory	Turmeric, Ginger, Cinnamon
6)	Anti Bacterial	Clove, Ginger, Thyme, Garlic, Lemon Balm, Fennel, Mint
7)	Anti Fungal	Neem Leaves, Turmeric, Honey, Yoghurt, Aloe vera
8)	Antibiotic	Manuka, Thyme, Olive leaf, Astragalus, Echinaceae
9)	Anti Microbial	Eucalyptus, Mallow, Garlic, Ginger, Primerose

2. Anatomy And Physiology Of The Skin :

Figure 3) Anatomy Of The skin.

Skin And Their Types :

The Surface of the human body is covered entirely by the skin. The major function of the skin are to protect the body from external environment, eliminate waste through sweating and regulate the body temperature. From a cosmetic point of view, the reference criteria are the users feelings and therefore the surface state of their skin and their capacity for seduction and even attraction. This selective criterion generally leads to classification of the skin into fourmaintypes, i.e., normal skin, oily skin, and mixed skin (Table 2).

Table 2. Skin Types And Their Care [7]

SR.NO.	Skin Type	Features	Suitable Skin Care	
			Herbal	Essential Oil
1)	Normal	Has even tone, soft, smooth texture, no visible pores or blemishes.	Pomegranate leaves juice, Herbal Face Pack	Lemon, Rose, Sandalwood, Lavender
2)	Dry	Low level of sebum and prone to sensitivity, Chapping and cracking are signs of extremely dry dehydrated skin.	Aloe Vera, Olive oil, Calendula Comfrey	Geranium, Almond, Lemon, Rose, Sandalwood, Lavender
3)	Oily	Shiny, Thick and dull coloured Chronically oily skin has coarse pores and pimples. Prone to black heads.	Aloe Vera, Oat Straw, Thyme, Lemon Grass, Cucumber	Geranium, Juniper, Lemon, Lavender
4)	Combination	Some part of your face are dry or flaky, while center part of your face is oily, and dry skin are present at the same time.	Witch Hazel, Menthol, Aloe Vera ,Turmeric Wheat Germ ,Sweet Flag	Citrus Oils, Jasmine Oil, Sandal Wood Oil

The skin of the human body consists of four parts viz,Epidemis, dermis, the fatty layer and the muscle layer. The importance of these parts with reference to the use of herbal cosmetics can be summarized as follows:

1)Epidermis:

The main outer layer of the skin known as epidermis, scurf skin or cuticles is made up of four to five thin layers composed of an intricate cellular system. Main layer of these various sub layers is known as basal layer, The cells of basal layer divides and gradually work to the surface where they shed themselves. Simulataneously the basal layer builds new cells which continues to carry out life processes of the skin. Lower layer of the epidermis is where skin colour is produced and the sunlight causes the melanocytes to become more active. Blochy discolorations can occur and larger freckles begin to appear as we get older. The superficial epidermal cells on the surface of the skin accumulate and thicken causing a dull, lifeless look.

Generally after the age of 30, less sebum, or natural oil and moisturizes are produced and the outer layer of the skin becomes dry and dull. Several treatments like bleaching, fineline therapy, exfoliation, hydration and use of sunscreen are recommended to reduce the appearance of surface wrinkles and discoloration.

2) Dermis:

Below the epidermis there lies the true skin which is called as courium or dermis layer. It is made up of three layers and contains tiny veins, sweat glands, hair bulbs and nerve endings. The blood vessels of the by the smaller vessels in the middle and the small capillaries mostly everywhere near the surface. These capillaries supply blood to the muscles glands, nails and hairs. The nerve endings are unequally networked being more numerous in locations like the lips or fingertips where the sense of touch is more prominent. The collagen and elastin fibers are also present in the basal layer and as skin are in three divisions varying as per the size. The largest blood vessels are in the deeper skin followed we age the slower blood flow causes breakdown of collagen and elastin which leads to sagging, and wrinkles that form, due to lack of collagen support.

Table 3. The structure, location and functions of sensory receptors in the epidermis and dermis of human skin.

Sr. No.	Sructure	Location	Function
1	Tree terminal	Epidermis, dermis	Sensation Of Itch And Pain, Fine discrimination for sensory stimuli in the digits.
2	Market Endings	Epidermis ridge	Mechanoreceptors for the sensation touch.
3	Meissenr touch corpuscles	Papillary dermis of palm hand and sole of foot	Sensation of touch and relative amounts of pressure associated with semsation of touch.
4	Paccinian /corpuscles	Deep layer's of palmar dermis palmar subcutaneous tissue, And near Periosteum of proximal phalanges	Sense of vibration, Signal's local changes in blood flow.
5	Pilo – Ruffini Corpuscles	Encircling the hair follicles	Slow reaching mechanoreceptors that responds to changes in pressure sensed by hair follicles, Ruffini end organ's also responsible for sensation warmth.
6	Krause and bulb	Superficial layers of the dermis	Sensation of cold.

Fatty Layer:

Directly beneath the dermal layer is a layer of fatty tissue which gives the skin its contour. As the fatty tissues which gives the skin its contour. As the fatty tissues disappears or becomes thinner through various processes like aging as we age on the face and neck, except on the jowls and sagging lower cheeks, which makes us look older.

Muscle Layer:

The deepest muscle layer is responsible for deep wrinkles caused by the buildup of grooved wrinkle lines caused from overuse of smiling and frowning. Chronic puckering and smoking and cause deep lines around the mouth. Some three million sweat glands secrete about one liter of perspiration every twenty four hours of a day.

The sebaceous glands almost equally distributed produce a semisolid fatty substance called as sebum which partially consists of cholesterolin and isocholesterin. This fatty substance resembles the animal fat lanolin which is generally used in the skin care preparations. The Surface of the skin is protected from rapid drying by virtue of the sebum. When it is secreted in insufficient quantities or when it dried up by excessive heat or very low.

Accessory Structure Of The Skin

It includes:Skin glands(It regulates body temperature), Hairs(It protect the body), Nails Itprotect the body.

A) Skin Glands :Thereare four types of exocrine gland within human skin – Sudoriferous, Sebaceous, Ceruminous and Memory glands.

B) Hairs :Hairs or pill are present on most skin surfaces except palms, fingers and feet surfaces Each hair is composed of columns of dead and keratinized cells bonded together by extracellular protein. The shaft is the superficial portion of the hair which projects above the surface of the skin.The root is the deeper portion of the hair that penetrates into the dermis and sometimes into the subcutaneous layer into the dermis. The shaft and root of the hair both consists of three concentric layers of cells.Medulla: Inner/made-up of soft keratin, Cortex: Middle/made-up of hard keratin.

Cuticle of the Hair: Surrounding the root hair is the hair follicle which is made-up of external root sheath and internal root sheath. Together these are referred as epithelial root sheath. The dense dermis surrounding the hair follicle is called as dermal root sheath. The base of each hairs follicle is an anion shaped structure called as bulb. The bulb contains nipple shaped structure called as papilla of the hair contains many blood vessels that nourishes the growing hair follicle. The function of hair is to keep out dust particles from entering the eyes, ear canals nasal chambers. Hair also acts as insulating coat of the human body as it keeps the body warm.

C) Nails:These are plates of tightly packed, hard, dead, keratinized epidermal cells over the dorsal surface of digits.Each nail consists of: Nail body: It is the visible portiort of nail.Free edge: It is the free part of nail.

Figure 4 : Nail Structure.

Nail root:

It is the portion that is buried in the fold of skin Below the nail body is the region of epithelium and deeper layer of dermis. Nail body appears pink in colour because of blood flowing through the capillaries in the dermis. The free edge is white in colour because of no blood capillaries. The whitish, crescent shaped area of the proximal end of nail body is called as lunula. Below, the free edge a thickened region of stratum corneum called as hyponychium, which secures the nail to the finger tip.

3. Historical Development Of Ayurvedic Product

The history of ayurveda came into existence when SrilaVyasadeva wrote vedas as per hindu mythology, origin of ayurveda considered to be divine from the hindu god Brahma, creator of the universe. Brahma passed this knowledge to Prajapati, one of the ten rishi's created by him; Prajapati communicated these ideas to rishi Indran and Athra, further to the next generation. Agnivesa compiled the knowledge from Vedas and it was Charak in Charaksamhita whichdescribes ayurvedic medicines and Susrutasmhita describing the science of surgery.

3.1. Prehistoric Period:

The lives of peoples of prehistoric times were determined by the spirits, they have no concept of public health. According to Anthropologist, the medicinal plants were used by the prehistoric peoples were Snake root plant, Yarrow (*Achilles millefolium*), Mallow, Birch polypore, Rosemary officinalis etc. Earth and clays were used internally and externally such as for treating wounds and also in surgery. Evidences suggest that those people were have knowledge of bone structure and they used to perform the brain surgery. The Snake root plant was used as tonic to calm the patients. Doctors in ancient India used to give extract of Foxgloves to the patients for treatment of heart ailments.

3.2. Buddhist Period Up To 10th Century:

(500 a.C-10th Century) In this period Ayurveda was well developed and encouraged by Buddha. Buddhist monk promoted ayurveda with traditional Chinese medicine. Nagarjuna, director of the University of Nalanda taught ayurveda including rasushastra, salyachikitsa. Surananda, Nagbodhi, Yashodhana, Nityanatha, Govinda, Anantdev, Vagbhata among other were successors of Nagarjuna. Chandragupta Maurya (321-297 BC) grandson's emperor Ashoka Samrat (273-236BC) had built many hospitals that contributed to the development of ayurveda.

In the 8th century, Madhav wrote a book called Nidana having 79 chapters which describes various diseases and their causes. Brndamadhava is a treatise on medicines having number of siddhas, yoga or prescription.

3.3. Period From 10th Century to 15th Century:

From 10th to 12th century, Invasion of Muslims specially in north India had destroyed Ayurveda killing 400 million Hindu & Buddhist 14,15 and imposed Unani system of medicine. MahavaNidana, Raja nighana and Madanpalanighantu were important works on Ayurveda.

3.4. Modern Period :

From 1835-36 begins the modern age of the Ayurveda, Madhusudan operated a human dead body. In 1836 he published Susrutasamhita. Kaviraj Haryana Chandra Chakravarthiji wrote a version of Sushrutasmhita Book. The Government of India had appointed the drug manufacturing committee in 1918 to explore the possibility of the cultivation of Medicinal plants in India thereby manufacturing drug on the large scale. Bhoire committee appointed by government of India in 1943 whose one of the recommendations was the development of the indigenous system of medicines like Ayurveda and Unani. After the independence the Central council for research & Ayurveda and Siddha (CCRAS) was formed. The Central council of Indian medicines (CCIM) was established. The CCRAS is under the control of CCIM. In 1959 the Drugs and Cosmetics (D & C) Act was amended to include drugs derived from traditional Indian medicine. In 1993, guidelines for the safety and efficacy of herbal medicines, which were incorporated in the Drug & Cosmetic Act and Rules were developed by expert committee. A drug is treated as a classical preparation if prepared as per any of the classical texts of Ayurveda which are mentioned in Schedule 1 of the Drug and Cosmetic Act, 1940. Schedule 1 is referred to in the GMP notification also in the context of labelling, packaging, limit of alcohol, maintenance of batch manufacturing records. In March 1995, The Department of Indian Systems of Medicine and Homoeopathy (ISM & H) was established under the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. [4]

3.5. The Organisation of Medical Care:

Side by side with the systematic development of medicines in ancient India, there was also organized medical help in the form of hospitals and dispensaries, and a certain measure of health propaganda. During the Buddhist period, monks travelled all over the country not only preaching religion and philosophy and dispelling ignorance, but also alleviating human suffering king. Asoka and his edicts are famous. But even before Asoka's time evidence of organized medical care was seen in CarakaSamhita. Vivid descriptions are found about the location, building, personnel and amenities of hospital-Aturalaya, a maternity home, Sutikargriha, a nursery Sugriha and a pharmacy. [5]

4. Development OF Ayurvedic Skin Care Product

It has been estimated that in developed countries such as United States, plants drugs comprise up to 25% of the total drugs, while in fast developing countries such as China and India, it comprise up to 80%. It is expected that there are 250,000 to 500,000 species of plants on Earth. Out of these small percentages (1 to 10%) are used as foods and medicine by both humans and animal. It is possible that rest of plant may be used for foods and medicinal purposes. Hence, it has turn out to be very important to review on herbal medicine which will play important role in research on plant to find their possible medicinal importance.

A herb is a plant or plant part utilized for its fragrance, flavor, or therapeutic properties. Natural prescriptions are one kind of dietary enhancement. They are sold as tablets, cases, powders, teas, removes, and new or dried plants. Individuals utilize home grown meds to attempt to keep up with or work on their wellbeing. Ayurveda utilizes numerous spices to make beautifying agents for beautification and security from outside impacts. The regular phytoconstituents not causes any incidental effects on the human body; yet give supplements and other helpful minerals to the body. Natural beautifiers or items are produced using different restorative fixings to shape the base in which at least one home grown fixings are fused for characterized corrective advantages. [7]

4.1. Importance of Natural Products for Drug Development:

The review of papers on the importance of natural products indicates that major investment is done in most of the developed and developing countries for development of new drugs from natural products. The salient features of the review indicate that About 47 major drugs are obtained from tropical plants. About 25 per cent of modern prescription drugs contain compounds derived from higher plants. Many important drugs are produced synthetically from natural product intermediates.

Out of about 120 pure compounds from higher plants used in medicine, two thirds are produced from temperate regions of the world. If alcohol, vinegar, citric acid, resorcinol like natural products be included, then the list of plant based medicinals may perhaps reach up to about 75 per cent.

Since the launch of large screening programmes in 1950s, the demand of pharmaceutical industry for natural products has experienced many ups and downs. In 1960s every company in the world screened a large number of natural products. But again in the 1970s, a decline was observed in the screening of natural products. In 1980s reinforcement of screening programmes of natural products was critically observed with further decline in the 1990s. The reasons for the shift of interest in natural products seem to lie in the changes in the supply of molecular diversity of natural products.

The beginning of the twenty first century once again generated the major rival of plant screening in general and indigenous systems of herbal medicine in particular for the search of new molecules with novel biological activities. There was a desperate need arising out of the following compelling reasons: i) The rate of discovery of new synthetic molecules as new drugs had tapered off ii) While synthetics and antibiotics were great life savers, the adverse side reactions of many synthetics and development of resistance to many antibiotics set the limit to the sole pursuit of synthetics and antibiotics.

WHO (World Health Organisation) officially started advocating the need of research into ethnic and indigenous systems of medicines which still caters to 80 per cent of medicinal needs of developing countries. The Bristol Mayor Squibb's breakthrough in Taxol from *Taxusbaccata* being catapulted into a billion dollar drug industry became an eye opener world wide to corporate multinational pharmaceutical sector.

Last but not least the green movement has given a tremendous support to the use of natural products, many of which are believed to be less toxic as compared to the synthetics. The peculiarities that make natural products so important and interesting are due to the fact that nature provides an enormous variation of extremely complex molecules, infinitely more sophisticated than any molecule from any other source. The specific qualities of natural products can be quoted in their uniqueness, unlimited structural diversity, complexity, patentability and the presence of a number of diverse chemical compounds in the single biological extract. This increases the probabilities to find a new pharmaceutical lead compared to homologous synthetic samples. [6]

4.2. World Trade and The Market:

The economical implications of natural products are also nonetheless interesting and encouraging. The pharmaceutical industry spends more on R & D than any other industry. Figures indicate that in 1995, USA alone spent more than US \$14 billion on R & D as compared to the total worldwide expenditure of about US \$23 billion. About 25 to 35 per cent of the R & D efforts are solely for the purpose of new drug discovery. The average cost of developing one new drug as per 1990 estimate is to the tune of US \$23 million in USA.

In most of the cases of new drugs of natural origin, quite attractive royalties ranging from about 1 to 15 per cent are paid for natural products. The product of early research may yield about 1 to 5 per cent of percentage of revenue to the supplier. However, in cases of clinical data, the efficacy data and identified lead molecules, the total revenue percentage goes from 10 to 15 per cent of the net sale. It appears that at least for the next few years, natural products will retain their importance because true innovative products are only expected to come from nature.

In several industrialised countries, plant- derived prescription drugs constitute a major element in the maintenance of health. Today, Germany, Bulgaria and Poland are recognised as major exporters of plant-based medicinal products. In Germany, for example, over 1500 plant species of 800 genera belonging to about 200 families have been processed into medicinal products. Hong Kong, Germany, Japan and Singapore are the highest importing countries in medicinal plant trade with an estimated share of 17.3, 12, 10.2 and 8.4 per cent, respectively, of the total import in the trade of medicinal plants. Europe represents huge reservoir of global herbal market constituting about 45 per cent of the total market followed by North America (18.2 per cent) and Asia (18.2 per cent).

The practice of traditional medicine is widespread in China, India, Japan, Pakistan, Sri Lanka and Thailand. In china about 40 per cent of the total drug material is attributed to traditional Chinese medicine. In Thailand the medicinal plants mostly from the families *Caesalpiniaceae*, *Fabaceae* and *Mimo- soideae* are used in herbal medicine. In Japan, herbal medicinal preparations are more in demand than mainstream pharmaceutical products.

In India, approximately 1700 plant species are used in Ayurveda, 500 for Siddha, 400 for Unani and 300 for Tibetan Amchi system of medicine with substantial overlaps of many common medicinal plants among these systems. The total number of plant species used in traditional systems of medicine in India touches to about 7500 and hence offer great scope in the world trade of medicinal plants and their products. Amazingly, India's share in world trade in medicinal and pharmaceutical products is merely 1.0 to 1.2 per cent since 1990. This situation exposes our weakness on the front of value addition.

The baseline question is world quality standards. Just meeting the in-house demand for preparation of Ayurvedic, Siddha, Unani and other traditional drugs cannot be the target. Even export of plant materials and extracts at a very low price cannot be viable. Value addition for novel therapeutic or related properties through systematic application can provide leadership to India in the global business of medicinal and aromatic plant wealth of the country. Different industrial uses like production of phytopharmaceuticals, galenicals, health food, intermediates for drugs and drug molecules are the value added products and India has a range of such products. [6]

4.3. Skin Hyperpigmentation And Its Treatment With Herbs :

Skin hyperpigmentation is a disorder in which patches of skin become darker in color than the normal surrounding skin. This occurs when melanin is overproduced in certain spots on the skin.

Causes of hyperpigmentation :

Hyper pigmentation is caused by many factors. These may be exogenous and endogenous factor like endocrinologic factor: Addison's disease, Cushing's syndrome, Nelson syndrome, Pheochromocytoma, Carcinoid, Acromegaly, Hyperthyroidism, Acanthosis nigricans, Diabetes. Nutritional factor: Kwashiorkor, Vitamin B12 deficiency, Folic acid deficiency, Niacin deficiency, Tryptophan deficiency, Vitamin A deficiency. Melasma is an undesirable skin effect on contraceptive use hormonal.

Treatment skin hyperpigmentation by herbs:

In addition to photosafety, there are several medications and treatments to treat hyperpigmentation of the skin of darker skin patients safely and efficiently with some adverse reactions. So, herbs and phytoconstituents are better choice for treatment for skin hyperpigmentation. Some herbs with their mechanism of action for treatment of skin hyperpigmentation. Hydroquinone, azelaic acid, kojic acid, liquoric extract, retinoids, etc., and treatments like chemexfoliation and laser therapy may be effective on their own properties, or in combination with other drugs. The possible mechanisms of actions by which herbs are used for the treatment of skin hyper pigmentation are namely tyrosinase inhibitory, antioxidant, and skin whitening effects. [8]

4.4. Management OF Psoriasis :

Psoriasis is a widespread skin condition where the skin develops areas that become thick. It is usually found to be covered with silvery scales. Psoriasis is considered as an autoimmune disease where genetic and environmental factors have a significant role. Psoriasis is a dry, inflammatory and ugly skin disorder, which can involve the entire system and is not contagious. The most frequently affected sites are the scalp, tips of fingers and toes, palms, soles, umbilicus, gluteus, under the breasts and genitals, elbows, knees, shin etc.

Types of psoriasis :

- 1) Plaque psoriasis (psoriasis vulgaris): It affects majority of people with psoriasis. Plaque psoriasis typically appears as raised areas of reddened skin covered with silvery white scaly skin.
- 2) Pustular psoriasis: Pustular psoriasis can be seen in localized, commonly to the hands and feet, or generalized with widespread patches occurring randomly on any part of the body.
- 3) Nail psoriasis: Produce a variety of changes in the appearance of finger and toe nails. These types of changes include discoloration under the nail plate, pitting of the nails, thickening of the skin under the nail, loosening (onycholysis) and crumbling of the nail.
- 4) Guttate psoriasis: It is characterized by copious small oval (teardrop-shaped) spots. They appear over large areas of the body, such as the trunk, limbs, and scalp. Guttate psoriasis is associated with streptococcal throat infection.
- 5) Flexural psoriasis (inverse psoriasis): It appears as smooth inflamed patches of skin. It is found in skin folds, mainly between the thigh and groin, the armpits, under an overweight stomach (pannus), and below the breasts (infra mammary fold).
- 6) Erythrodermic psoriasis: It involves the extensive inflammation and exfoliation of the skin over most of the body surface and may be accompanied by severe itching, swelling and pain. It is often the result of an exacerbation of unstable plaque psoriasis, particularly after the abrupt withdrawal of systemic treatment. This type of psoriasis may be fatal, because more rigorous inflammation and exfoliation disturb the body's ability to regulate temperature and for the skin to perform barrier functions

Ayurvedic Treatment For Psoriasis:

- 1) Olive oil: Olive oil is an effective treatment for mild cases of plaque psoriasis. It can be massaged directly onto affected areas of the skin to reduce dryness and irritation as well as to facilitate healing. Olive oil is reported to have antioxidant properties (vitamin E), which will be of use in the case of psoriasis, since free radicals have been linked to psoriasis outbreaks.
- 2) Milk thistle: Extract of Milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*), is also known as silymarin, is suggested by alternative medical practitioners to stimulate bile production in the liver and also to regulate the immune system. The herb keeps the blood clean and protects the liver, which makes it an effective psoriasis Remedy.
- 3) *Calendula officinalis*: It is a short-lived aromatic herbaceous perennial. The leaves are oblong-lanceolate, hairy on both sides and with margins entire or irregularly waved or weakly toothed. *Calendula officinalis* belonging to the Family Compositae is some of the very common Indian herbs having various medicinal properties for the treatment of different kind of disease, viz. antifungal, wound healing and antidiabetic agents respectively.
- 4) *Coleus*: Although there is less scientific evidence, the Ayurvedic herb *coleus* (*Coleus Forskohlii*) has been used historically as one of many herbal psoriasis remedies. *Coleus* is valuable in treating skin disorders such as psoriasis due to its ability to promote normal cell division. *Cayenne* (*Capsicum annum*) has been regarded by many experts as an effective natural psoriasis remedy. His herb contains a substance known as capsaicin, which by depleting neurotransmitters from the sensory nerves, relieves pain and itching associated with psoriasis.
- 5) *Aloe Vera*: According to a double-blind study published in *Tropical Medicine & International Health* in 1996, the topical application of *aloe Vera* is a very safe and natural psoriasis remedy. Patients who participated in the trial experienced a severer reduction in lesions and many were considered "healed" by researchers after four weeks of treatment. No adverse reactions were reported. [9]

Flowchart 5 :The Actions Of Ayurveda Drugs In Psoriasis [10]

4.5. Environmental skin disorders :

Photodamage is a type of skin disorder that arises from the exposure of the skin to solar light or UVR which includes erythema, edema, hypermelanogenesis, oxidative stress, inflammation, immunosuppression, and further development of cutaneous malignancies.

Erythema (sunburn)

Erythema is an acute inflammatory response to continuous UVR exposure. The severity of erythema depends upon the rate and extent of skin exposure to UVR .

Hypermelanogenesis

UVR exposure to the skin may result in immediate pigmentation or delayed pigmentation response. UVR exposure to the skin elevates melanin synthesis, which increases number and activity of melanocytes, leading to the deposition of melanin granules in the upper layers of the epidermis.

UVR -induced epigenetic alterations:

Epigenetics is the modification in gene expression, function, and generation of a heritable phenotype irrespective of change in DNA sequence. UVR-induced histone acetylation contributes to the UVR transcriptional response. Epigenetic alterations are reversible, and therefore dietary food or bioactive compounds may have the ability to reverse, inhibit or delay the epigenetic modifications for the prevention of the disease.

UVR induced microRNAs regulation

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are small non-coding RNAs which act as a regulator in post-transcriptional modifications. Recent studies show that miRNAs have been explored as a therapeutic target against UVR-induced cellular responses. The diversity of miRNA targets determines their involvement in various cellular networks. miRNAs have shown to regulate many biological processes such as cell differentiation, proliferation, and apoptosis.

UVR-induced DNA damage and repair

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated by UVR irradiation can indirectly damage DNA bases which lead to dimerization and is considered as the biomarker of oxidative DNA damage. The injury persists beyond repair leading to cell death by induction of the apoptosis pathway. If the DNA damage continues in the S-phase of the cell cycle, there is an increase in proliferation which ultimately leads to skin carcinogenesis. [11]

Flowchart 6 :Effects Of UVR On The Skin.

4.6. Herbal skin care products as a therapeutic alternative:

Herbal skincare products are now-a-days more preferred and chosen by people because of their fewer side-effects and cost-effectiveness. Traditionally, herbal products are applied to a particular area or a part of the skin for the treatment of various skin ailments. The topical formulations can be classified into creams, gels, ointments, lotions, and foams. The herbal products exhibit various therapeutic properties such as anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-viral, cardio-protective, neuroprotective, and hepato-protective properties. Many plants-derived natural molecules such as alkaloids, flavonoids, isoflavones, proanthocyanidins, phenolic compounds, and essential oils are associated with the treatment of many dermatological disorders. Several herbal products have been uncovered for their therapeutic potential against UV irradiation and are gaining considerable attention. The photoprotective properties of such herbal products regarding safety and efficacy need to be validated as per the regulatory guidelines which follows internationally accepted scientific principles. It is requisite for the development of such herbal skincare products possessing strong therapeutic potential for the treatment of UVB-induced skin disorders and a better quality of life. The combination of different herbal products may result in their synergistic effect. This will further help in pre-clinical and clinical investigations in the area of dermatology. [11]

5. Preparation method And Standardization Method Of Ayurvedic Formulation:

Ayurvedic formulations can be categorized into four types based on their physical nature of dosage forms: Solid dosage forms (e.g. Ghutika), Semi solid dosage forms (e.g. Leha), Liquid dosage forms (e.g. Asava, Arishta), Powder dosage forms (e.g. Bhasma, Churna).

5.1. Aristas And Asavas :

They are also known as preparations containing self generated alcohol (alcoholic preparation) they are prepared by adding powder drug or its decoction into a solution of sugar or jaggery it is then fermented for a specified time during which alcohol is generated which facilitates the extraction of active principles present in the drugs. The self generated alcohol also act as a preservative.

Both Aristas and Asavas are self generating alcoholic preparations but they differ in the methods of preparation. Aristas are prepared by extracting the powder drug in the form of decoction and then added to the solution of sugar or jaggery. Asavas are prepared by directly adding the powder drugs into the solution of sugar or jaggery, the remaining process of preparation remains the same

Method of preparation of Aristas:

The crude drugs are coarsely powder and decoction (kashaya) is prepared and filtered. Other ingredients are mixed with the decoction and these contents are added to a solution of sugar or jaggery or honey. It is then boiled, cooled and transferred to wooden barrels. The mouth of the container is covered with an earthen lid and the edges are sealed with clay smeared clothe which is found in seven consecutive layers. The container is kept in an underground cellar or a heap of paddy in order to ensure a constant temperature is maintain during the process of fermentation. After the specified period, the lid is remove and the contents are examined in ensure that the process of fermentation has been completed. The fluid is filter and stored.

Method of preparation of Asavas :

The drug is finely powdered and mixed with other ingredients and these contents are added to a solution of sugar or jaggery or honey, mixed well. If it is then boiled, cooled and transferred to wooden barrels or pots. The mouth of the container is covered with an earthen lid and the edges are sealed with clay smeared cloth which is wound in seven consecutive layers. The container is kept in an underground cellar or a heap of paddy in order to ensure a constant temperature is maintained during the process of fermentation. After the specified period the lid is removed and the contents are examined to ensure that the process of fermentation (Sandhana) has been completed. The fluid is filtered and stored.

Standardization parameters for Aristas and Asavas:

Aristats and Asavas should be clear without any froth or foam at the top It should not becomes sour upon standing. It should have a characteristic aromatic and alcoholic odour. There should be no effervescence produced. Ex : Aristas: Ashokarista, Dasmularista, Ashwagandhaarista. Asavas: Arvindasava, Kumaryasava, Vasakasava

5.2. Vati and Ghutika:

These are medicines in the form of tablets (vati) and pills ghutika). They contain single or combinations of herbal, miners or animal drugs.

Method of preparation:

The drugs are dried and finely powdered, mineral drugs are converted into calcinated products (Bhasmas) or any other form as specified. As per the mentioned formula, the drugs and other ingredients are mixed together and made into a soft paste with specified liquids. It is then properly ground and made into vati (tablets) or ghutikas (Pills).

Standardization parameters for Vati and Ghutika:

Vati and Ghutika should be stable up to 2 years after preparation. If they contain only mineral ingredients, they can be used indefinitely. They should not lose their original colour, odour, taste and form upon storage. If they contain sugar/salt, they should be protected from moisture.

5.3. Churna:

They contain single or combination of drugs along with other ingredients in a powdered form.

Method of preparation:

Drugs and other ingredients mentioned in the formula are separately dried, finely powdered and sieved to get uniform size particles, they are mixed to get a uniform powder.

Standardization parameters for Churna:

Churnas should be free flowing powders and should not adhere or become moist. Churnas are stable up to one year if they are stored properly. Fine the powder, better is its potency and therapeutic value. Eg: Triphalachurna, Drakshailchurna, Sudarshanchurna.

5.4. Leha / Avaleha:

These are semisolid preparations made by boiling the powdered drug/ extract with a solution of sugar or jaggery.

Method of preparation:

Sugar/jaggery is dissolved in a liquid, it is boiled and filtered. The powdered drugs/ extract along with other ingredients are added with continuous stirring to form a homogenous semisolid mass. If necessary ghee or oil is also added while the preparation is hot.

Standardization parameters for Leha:

It should neither become hard nor liquify. There should be no growth of fungus over it. It should not change its colour, odour and taste. They can be used up to one year if properly stored. E.g. Draksavaleha, Vasavaleha, Bilvadileha.

5.5. Bhasma:

These are the powdered forms of drugs prepared by calcination (heating the solids in air to change its original form) of metals, minerals or animal products by a special process in closed crucibles or in pits covered with cow dung.

Method of preparation:

They are prepared in two stages :

a) Sodhana: It is a process of purification of metals, minerals by heating them and immersing in a specific liquid. This is done to remove its toxicity.

b) Marana: This is the second stage of preparing bhasmas, in which the purified drugs obtained from sodhana process are ground and mixed with plants/ extracts as specified. After specified time, small cakes are made and dried in sunlight. The dried cakes are kept in earthen vessels, sealed with clay smeared cloth and kept in a pit covered with cow dung and the fire is put on all the sides. After heating for a specified period, the contents are removed and ground into a fine powder and stored

Standardization Parameters For Bhasmas:

Bhasmas are grey, whitish, yellowish or black coloured powders. They should not change their colour on storage. They are highly stable for long periods and should not lose their potency. Eg: Suvarnabhasma, Shankhabhasma, Taurabhasma, Suvarnabhasma, Shankhabhasma, Taurabhasma.

Table 4 :Ayurveda Formulation For Skin Care [12].

S.No.	Types of Formulation	Example
1	Rasousadha	Arogyavardhiniras, Pittalarasayana and Tarakeswara
2	Natural Powder	Pancanimbachurna
3	Paste	SomarajiGhrita
4	Avaleha	BhallatakAvaleha
5	Asava- Arista	Madhwasava
6	Lepa	TriphaladiLepa, VayasyadiLepa

5.6. Traditionally used plants for skin disorders:

Plant-derived products have been used for medicinal purposes for centuries and the earliest records from 2900e2600 BC document the use of approximately 1000 plants, such as oil of Cedrus species (cedar), Commiphoramyrtha (myrrh), Cupressus sempervirens (cypress), Glycyrrhizaglabra (Liquorice), and Papaversomniferum (opium). Various natural phytoingredients (curcumin, silymarin, ginkgo biloba) have been exploited for their cellular protective effects with the detailed mechanisms in different experimental models. Herbal products from the plant's sources for cosmetic or skin pathological states have always been popular because of several advantages such as fewer side-effects, better patient tolerance, being cheaper and acceptable due to the long history of use. These include aloe vera, grapevine, ginseng, green tea, tea tree oil, rosemary, lemon, soybean, papaya, garlic, ginkgo, olive oil, and Ocimum. [11]

Table 5. Ayurvedic Skin Care Product

Sr.No.	Product Name	Brand Name	Active Ingredients	Benefits
1)	Soundarya Radiance Cream	Forest Essentials	Liquorice Root Extract Ghee, Gold Bhasma, Saffron	-Deeply Moisturizes the skin, -Controls collagen depletion, Improves elasticity and firmness.
2)	Rejuvenating And Brightening Night Cream	Kama Ayurveda	Aloevera, Mulaithi, Saffron, Manjistha	-Skin Brightening -Pigmentation -Minimize Dark Circles
3)	Natural Sun Protection	Kama Ayurveda	Ginger, Olive Oil, Shea Butter, Lime, Nutmeg	To Protect Skin From Damage
4)	Neem Powder (AzadirachtaIndica)	Banyan Botanicals	Neem	It Cleanses and Purifies And Supports Healthy Blood And Liver Functions
5)	NeemVarnyaLepa	Forest Essentials	Clove, Neem, Vitamin E, Manjistha	Clarifies the pores by removing excess oil Reduce Acne and helps decrease blackhead
6)	Skin Foods Glow Mix	Kavipa	Rose, Shatavari, Mulethi, Pomegranate	Helps promote radiant skin Increases collagen production that reduces fines lines and wrinkles Reduces Pigmentation
7)	ChandanVarnyaLepa	Forest Essentials	Saffron, Honey, Kokum Butter Nageskar	Tones and firms the skin Deeply hydrates and rejuvenates
8)	Advanced Sanjeevani Beauty Elixir	Forest Essentials	Kokum Butter, Aloevera, Sweet Almond Oil	Revives damaged skin cells Instantly penetrates and plumps the skin
9)	Ayurvedic Vitamin C Serum	Sadhev The Art Of Ayurveda	Amla, Pomegranatem, Seed Oil	Reduction of blemishes and Improves uneven skin tone Tightens the skin and prevents acne
10)	Plant Retinol Cream	Lotus Organics	Lotus	Ultimate skin hydration Refines skin texture

6. Present Perspective For Skin Care Product :

In the recent decades, Ayurveda has experienced a considerable shift in its paradigm and a significant change in the outlook of researchers, towards its applications has occurred. The therapeutic principles of Ayurveda focus on prakriti and tridoshas, and these principles explain that every individual has his unique constitution called as prakriti. Prakriti determines the characteristic response of each individual to medications, environmental conditions and dietary factors. 'Ayurgenomics' a recently introduced research field, bridges this gap between genomics and Ayurveda and serves as an aid in understanding of inter-individual differences in responses to therapies in various diseases. It especially emphasizes on studying inter-individual variances in patients from identical ethnic backgrounds. [13]

Herbal products have triggered the demand for natural products and natural extracts in cosmetics preparation, because there is common belief that chemical based cosmetics are harmful to the skin. By the excessive use of synthetic based products, synthetic chemicals, chemical dyes and their derived products in the last one and half century, their production and usage cause human health hazard with several side-effects leading to numerous diseases. The concept of beauty is not only for women alone, but even men have also become aware about their look. Now a day's advertisements of many face washes and fairness cream are aimed at men. The face skin beauty of individuals depends on the health, routine job, habits, conditions and maintenance. The extreme winter cause damage to the skin in the form of cracks, cuts, infections and maceration. The skin due to excessive exposure to heat will dehydrate during summer and causes wrinkle, blemishes, pigmentation, freckles and sunburns. To make cosmetics for beautification and protection from external affects, the science of Ayurveda had utilized many herbs and floras. The natural content in the botanicals does not cause any side effects on the human body, instead enrich the body with nutrients and other useful minerals. The new markets are being driven by fundamental shift in demand for herbal-based products and renewed concern about the synthetic-based products.

Chemicals and synthetic ingredients, used in many skincare and cosmetic products, can cause a variety of undesirable side effects, especially for people with sensitive skin and potential allergic reactions. The overwhelming array of synthetic and potentially harmful ingredients used in skincare and cosmetic products (health hazards associated phthalates, parabens, petroleum based chemicals, aluminum salts, etc.) are main reason for freshly produced organic and natural skincare, based on innovative and up to date multifunctional and effective formulations which include products with anti-aging, skin lightening and super moisturizing benefits. Large corporations are also attempting to follow the natural trend, due to consumer requirements.

The most recent news is that the first time Procter and Gamble (P&G) has published a list of 140 fragrances which they no longer use in their products, which, according to the Environmental Working Group (EWG), are linked to endocrine disruption, reproductive toxicity and cancer. In order to create a natural and/or organic formulation, plant derived bioactive compounds from essential oils, cold pressed vegetable oils, natural resins, extracts and other natural; raw materials are combined with plant derived emulsifiers, surfactants, humectants, pigments and other ingredients. Taking into consideration the huge variety of the market supply of organic plant derived ingredients which are often adulterated with synthetic or toxic intermediates. [14]

7. Future Perspective For Skin Care Product :

TSMs are now been looked upon for recourse to some limitations faced by western medicine, such as the need for individualized therapies, potential side effects and lack of desired therapeutic efficacy. Several studies correlating the concept of prakriti in Ayurveda to present-day science. A report indicating the correlation of dominant prakriti with the Body Mass Index (BMI) and place of birth in individuals was published.

Studies involving subjects of various prakriti types viz. Vata, Pitta and Kapha, were carried out to identify molecular differences that affect susceptibility and responses of individuals to various environmental or disease conditions. A classification method for human population, with respect to DNA methylation signatures is reported based upon traditional Ayurveda concept of prakriti. In a study involving genome-wide SNP (single nucleotide polymorphism) in 262 male individuals from three different prakritis, it was found that PGM1 gene is associated with energy production. PGM1 was found to be more homogeneous in Pitta prakriti, than the Kapha and Vataprakriti. [13]

There is a large international demand for the development of anti-aging, UV protective, whitening and extra moisturizing natural skincare products. The anti-aging skin care products trend is moving towards developing new botanical ingredients and intermediates targeting specific needs, based on discoveries, and advanced technologies. In case of anti aging products, the age-related decline in skin regenerative cells is a result of homeostatic imbalance, cutaneous disorders, environmental factors. Skin exposure to UV radiations cause oxidative stress, inflammation, wrinkling, skin cancer, erythema, edema, sunburn and photoaging and can lead to generation of toxic compounds and reactive free radicals, which can cause damages to DNA in nuclei and mitochondria, deterioration of membranes, lipids and proteins in skin-resident stem/progenitor and following cell dysfunctions. There are quite a few natural compounds, which can prevent from UV damage: α -tocopherol which prevents UVA- and UVB-induced glutathione loss and reduce induction of DNA damage by UVB. β -Carotene which inhibits free radicals and cause higher resistance to immunosuppression after exposure to UV light ; lycopene which absorb light in the UV range and increase the toughness of the skin. Lutein which prevent extracellular matrix breakdown and prevents skin from UV damage; flavonoids such as isorhamnetin, quercetin, kaempferol which significantly decreased erythema developed after UVB irradiation, and green tea polyphenols which reduce UV-induced p53 expression and keratinocytes apoptosis and protect from DNA damage, and others. Among the other natural plant derived compounds, polyphenols (for example from green and black tea) are shown to promote the degradation of melanin causing depigmentation effect on animal skin in vitro.

The research challenges in natural personal products trend are including creation of a perfect ratio between the natural plant derived ingredients and bio actives, which will provide great product absorption, proper moisture balance, effective and improved cellular metabolism including hormonal and chemical skin reactions, efficient hydration, proper exfoliation, effective circulation and cellular nutritional support, enhanced lymphatic functions and detoxification of the skin. There are no doubts that global natural and organic personal care products market is growing, significantly expanding and by Grand View research Inc, is expected to reach USD 15.98 billion by 2020. North American and International companies are undertaking strategic initiatives to increase presence and percentage of the natural skincare and cosmetic products on the Global market. Instead of synthetic products, North American and International consumers prefer organic and natural non toxic and environment friendly personal care products which definitely represent the major stream in personal care and cosmetic industry. [14]

DISCUSSION:

Ayurveda has its own approach for skin care which is related with healthy status of body as well as mind. There is greater demand of Ayurveda in the field of skin care due to adverse effect and limitations of modern science.

There are various skin care product in Ayurveda like vati (arogyavardhini vati), ghutika, asava arishta (madhwasa), leha, bhasma, lepa(triphaladi lepa, vayasyadi lepa) are used. These product have rakta shodhan properties and appropriate for each type of skin. Various plant parts are used to treat dermatologic condition in India. i.e. rhizomes, root's, stem, Flower's, Fruit, Bark, Seed, Buds, Latex and whole plant parts. Topical administration takes the form more complex preparation i.e. decoction's, infusion's, ointments, oil's, tinctures, powder etc.

Today, the best established and most widely recognised skin care product uses are based on its merits as Anti bacterial, Anti-inflammatory, Anti- parasitic , analgesic, wound healing, and antifungal properties that not only gives benefits to health but also solves many Beauty problems . Ayurvedic preparation are reported efficacious against a variety of skin diseases septic sores and infected burns.

This review presents that different herb's use to treat various skin diseases like hyperpigmentation, leprosy, psoriasis, erythema, hypermelanogenesis. UVR induced epigenetic alterations, UVR induced micro RNA's regulation, UVR Induced DNA damage and repair. There are several medications and treatments to treat hyperpigmentation of the skin with some adverse effects so, herbs and phyto constituents are better choice for treatment of hyperpigmentation e.g. liquorice extract, retinoids etc. Psoriasis is a wide spread skin conditions where the skin develops areas that become thick, for treatment of different herb's are used like olive oil , Aloe Vera, calendula officinalis. Medicines for the psoriasis treatment in Ayurveda are agnitudi vati, raktshodhak vati and talekt.

Herbal skin care product now a days more preferred and chosen by the people because of their fewer side effect and cost effectiveness, better patient tolerance, cheaper and acceptable due to long history of use. It includes Ashwagandha, Aloe Vera, turmeric, grapevine, ginseng, green tea, liquorice root, rosemary, lemon, papaya, garlic, olive oil etc. There are different types of skin oily and dry skin. Applying sunscreen lotion for protection and using moisturizing creams for cold climate. This review shows that the knowledge of herbal medicine is being used to treat different kinds of human skin disorder by local people. In Indian continent, complementary therapy for dermatological problems and treatment remains the main option for billion's of people.

Ayurvedic skin care product are mostly used because of their common belief that chemical based products are harmful to the skin to make cosmetics for beautification and protection from external affects, the science of Ayurveda and had utilised many Herb's and Flora's. There is large international demand for the development of Anti aging, UV protective, whitening and extra moisturizing natural skin care product. Ayurveda has its own approach for skin care, which is related with healthy status of body as well by mind. This review explain that large number of herbs and other naturally obtained raw material have been formulated as skin care product.

While selecting the drug for proper skin care Ayurvedic as well as modern both the aspects are taken into consideration. The use of bioactive ingredient's influence biological functions of skin and provide nutrients necessary for healthy skin. The knowledge of medicinal plants mentioned in Ayurvedic text is very helpful in the development of various skin care product.

The medicinal plants used in skin care product has not only the potential to enhance beauty but they also have medicinal properties due to presence of multiple chemical constituent. These chemical constituents may give additional benefit to treat various skin related problems, so using medicinal plants for skin care product may give some desired medicinal benefit for skin and body apart from their cosmetic effect. As the demand is rising for skin care herbal product over synthetic product. Some antioxidants, vitamins and fixed oil found to be responsible for cosmetic effects of selected medicinal plants.

CONCLUSION

Most of the skin care product containing chemicals and synthetic ingredients are available in the market may produce side effect and damage to the skin. Ayurvedic product like Lepa, Powder, Churna, Vati, Asava, Arishta, etc are made with natural ingredient that are gentle on the skin and are less likely to cause breakdown and other skin irritation. These product are safe for longer period of time.

There are various herb's are used present in the nature that improves the skin health and used in the treatment of various Skin disorder's like Psoriasis, Leprosy, Eczema, Skin Hyperpigmentation, mostly used. Herbs for derma care are Turmeric, Aloe vera, Cinnamon, Ginger, etc.

This review may help's in personal care Industry, Markets and Modern Scientist to understand different trend's of potential used to research on Ayurvedic Product's for skin care.

REFERENCE

- 1) Gupta, K., 2019. Ayurvedic regimes for skin care – A conceptual study. *Int. Ayu. Med. J.* 7(11), p.2114.
- 2) Pandey, Y.K., Meena, A., Gaur, M.B. and Sabharwal, P., 2019. Dermatological manifestations in Ayurveda: A review. *Eur. J. Pharm. Med. Res.*, 6, pp.277-93.
- 3) Uttapal A., Tudu, C.K., Nandy, S., Sunita, K., Tripathi, V., Loake, G.J., Dey, A. and Proćków, J., 2022. Ethnodermatological use of medicinal plants in India: from ayurvedic formulations to clinical perspectives—a review. *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 284, p.114744.
- 4) Tiwari, S.B., Singh, S.D., Verma, A.K., Awasthi, D. and Rastogi, A.K., 2021. History of Ayurvedic System of Medicines: From Prehistoric to Present. *J. Drug. Deliv. Thera.*, 11(1-s), pp.212-214.
- 5) Narayanaswamy, V., 1981. Origin and development of ayurveda:(a brief history). *Anc. Sci. Life.*, 1(1), p.1.
- 6) Rangari, V.D., 2009. *Pharmacognosy & phytochemistry* Vol. 2, pp. 66-75.
- 7) Ale, Y., Kushwaha, A. and Singh, A., 2021. A Review On Herbal Drugs As Skin Care Products, *Eur. J. Mol. Clin. Med.*, 8(04), p.2021.
- 8) Rathee, P., Kumar, S., Kumar, D., Kumari, B. and Yadav, S.S., 2021. Skin hyperpigmentation and its treatment with herbs: an alternative method. *Future. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 7(1), pp.1-14.
- 9) Abraham, N., Krishnan, N. and Raj, A., 2019. Management of psoriasis-ayurveda and allopathy-A review. *Int. J. Dermatol. Clin. Res.*, 5(1), pp.018-023.
- 10) Nille, G.C. and Chaudhary, A.K., 2021. Potential implications of Ayurveda in Psoriasis: A clinical case study. *J. Ayu. Int. Med.*, 12(1), pp.172-177.
- 11) Sharma, R.R., Deep, A. and Abdullah, S.T., 2021. Herbal products as skincare therapeutic agents against ultraviolet radiation-induced skin disorders. *J. Ayu. Integr. Med.*, p.100-500.
- 12) Gupta, R.K., Sharma, P.K., Pandey, A.D., Gupta, M.K. and Mujhalda, U., 2018. Ayurveda perspective of Skin care : a review on cosmeceuticals and traditional formulation. *Eur. J. Biomed. Pharm.*, 5(5), pp.1110-1113.
- 13) Jaiswal, Y.S. and Williams, L.L., 2017. A glimpse of Ayurveda—The forgotten history and principles of Indian traditional medicine. *J. Tradit. Complement. Med.*, 7(1), pp.50-53.
- 14) Emerald, M., Emerald, A., Emerald, L. and Kumar, V., 2016. Perspective of natural products in skincare. *Pharm. Pharmacol. Int. J.*, 4, p.72.

54878478451230209

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

